

Studies on reaction of hydroxycoumarin compounds with formamide

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3-Hydroxycoumarin, on reaction with hot formamide, produced 3-formylaminocoumarin (2) which underwent deformylation on fusion with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid monohydrate to produce very pure variety of 3-aminocoumarin. 4-Hydroxycoumarin and 4-hydroxybenzo[*b*]thiopyran-2-one (7) on similar reaction produced benzo[1]pyrano[4,3-*d*]oxazol-4-one (6) and benzo[1]thiopyrano[4,3-*d*]oxazol-4-one (8) respectively, under effectively non-oxidising reaction condition.

Coumarin compounds are known to possess various physiological activities¹, among them, mention may be made of their anthelmintic, hypnotic, insecticidal, antifungal, blood-anticoagulant and diuretic properties. A plethora of synthetic researches have been pursued on this class of compounds². Synthetic works on coumarins with oxazole³, isoxazole⁴, isoxazoline⁴ and isothiazole⁵ fused along the C3-C4 bond of the coumarin ring are reported. Recently, Mulwad and Shirodkar⁶ have reported coumarins fused with isoxazole and pyrimidine along the C3-C4 bond of the coumarin ring; synthesis of these compounds started from suitable 3,4-disubstituted coumarins. 4-Mercaptocoumarin-3-amide undergoes oxidative ring-

closure with bromine in ethyl acetate to furnish benzopyrano[3,4-*d*][1,2]isothiazole-3,4-dione⁵. A report describes synthesis of 2-methyl- benzopyrano[3,4-*d*]thiazol-4-one by way of intramolecular cyclodehydrogenation of 3-thioacetamidocoumarin. We report, herein, synthesis of benzo[1]pyrano[4,3-*d*]oxazol-4-one (6) and benzo[1]thiopyrano[4,3-*d*]oxazol-4-one (8) from 4-hydroxycoumarin and 4-hydroxybenzo[1]thiopyran-2-one (7) respectively by way of oxidative ring-closure of the oxazole ring in an apparently non-oxidising reaction condition.

In an early report⁸, formation of 3-iminomethyl-4-

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

hydroxycoumarin by reaction of 4-hydroxycoumarin with formamide at 140–150° was described. The queer functional nature of the structure reported for the product attracted our interest and we surmised reinvestigation of the nature of the products in case of reaction of coumarin compounds bearing hydroxy substituent in the pyrone/thiopyrone rings.

Results and discussion

Reaction of 3-hydroxycoumarin (**1**) with formamide at 160° produced 3-formylaminocoumarin (**2**) (Scheme 1); it shows two stretching absorptions at 1670 and 1710 cm^{-1} in its IR spectrum corresponding to the C=O chromophores of the formylamino group and the coumarin respectively and very sharp absorption at 3340 cm^{-1} for the NH stretching. Heating **2** with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid monohydrate at 135–140° for 2 h followed by treatment with aqueous ammonia led to production of 3-aminocoumarin (**3**) in a very pure state unmixed with any 3-hydroxycoumarin. This complements the hydrolysis of 3-acetamidocoumarin (**4**) with hot aqueous hydrochloric acid which invariably furnished **3** accompanying an appreciable amount of 3-hydroxycoumarin as a second product⁹. 3-Acetamidocoumarin (**4**) also produced 3-aminocoumarin (**3**) unmixed with **1** under the condition of fusion with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid monohydrate at 140–145°. In its ¹H NMR spectrum **2** shows two singlets at δ 8.63 and 8.50 for the formyl proton and 4-H of the coumarin ring respectively, and a broad singlet at δ 8.21 for the NH proton. In its ¹³C NMR spectrum, in addition to methine-carbon signals at δ 129.27, 127.83, 124.69, 127.83 and 116.41 for C-4, C-5, C-6, C-7 and C-8 respectively, and quaternary carbon signals at δ 157.80, 123.21, 119.60 and 150.25 for C-2, C-3, C-4a and C-8a respectively, **2** shows a doublet at δ 159.48 for the methine carbon of NHCHO moiety.

Reaction of 4-hydroxycoumarin (**5**) with formamide at 140° for 2 h led to subsequent isolation of a single product whose structure has been arrived at from spectral analysis as benzo[1]pyrano[4,3-*d*]oxazol-4-one (**6**). In

its IR spectrum a strong stretching absorption occurs at 1700 cm^{-1} for the C=O chromophore of the coumarin moiety; in its ¹H NMR spectrum, a singlet at δ 8.43 appears for the 2-H of the oxazole moiety. The conclusive information is extracted from its ¹³C NMR spectrum which contains methine carbon signals appearing at δ 117.05, 125.49, 124.08 and 134.51 assignable to C-6, C-7, C-8 and C-9 respectively, and a methine carbon signal at δ 162.25 assignable to C-2, the quaternary carbon signals for C-3a, C-5a, C-9a and C-9b appeared at δ 125.89, 154.44, 120.58 and 160.61 respectively. The ¹³C NMR signal positions may be compared with those of 4-hydroxycoumarin (**5**) and 3-hydroxycoumarin (**1**)¹⁰ to profit, for assignment of the oxazole moiety along C3-C4 bond of the coumarin ring. This construction of the oxazole ring in an effective non-oxidising reaction condition may be rationalized in Scheme 2. Triggering of nucleophilic reaction at C-3 by the hydroxy group of C-4 in 4-hydroxycoumarin (**5**) is commonplace¹¹.

In a similar reaction of 4-hydroxybenzo[*b*]thiopyran-2-one¹² (**7**) with formamide at 160° for 1 h, the product is benzo[1]thiopyrano[4,3-*d*]oxazol-4-one (**8**) (Scheme 2). In its IR spectrum a strong stretching absorption occurs at 1675 cm^{-1} for the carbonyl chromophore at C-4. In the ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra C-2 methine signals appear at δ_{H} 9.43 and δ_{C} 150.09. The ¹³C NMR data of **8** are compared with **7** in Table 1. In the SFORD spectrum of **8**, the C2-H coupling value is 177.2 Hz, for C6-H it is 172.8 Hz and for the three other C-H of the benzene ring the coupling constant values lie in the range of 160–163 Hz; these values may be compared with the ²J_H values for C-5, C-6, C-7 and C-8 signals of **7**, obtainable at 163.9, 164.03, 163.62 and 164.5 Hz. In the spectra, C-4a and C-8a quaternary carbons of **7** appear as multiplets; the same situation occurs with the C-5a and C-9a of **8**, which are correspondingly situated.

Experimental

The melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken as KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectropho-

Table 1. ¹³C NMR chemical shift values of 4-hydroxybenzo[*b*]thiopyran-2-one (**7**) and benzo[1]thiopyrano[4,3-*d*]oxazol-4-one (**8**)

4-Hydroxy- benzo[<i>b</i>]thiopyran- 2-one (7)	C-2 :	C-3 :	C-4 :	C-4a :	C-5 :	C-6 :	C-7 :	C-8 :	C-8a :
	180.71	103.31	167.09	123.83	131.44	126.03 ^a	126.62	126.38 ^a	136.66
Benzo[1]thiopy- rano[4,3- <i>d</i>]oxazole- 4-one (8)	C-4 :	C-3a :	C-9b :	C-9a :	C-9 :	C-8 :	C-7 :	C-6 :	C-5a :
	178.87	125.80	163.77	136.79	132.74	129.17 ^a	128.78 ^a	127.92 ^a	132.74

^aExchangeable.

tometer and UV spectra of ethanolic solutions of the compounds were recorded on a Hitachi U-200 spectrophotometer. The ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compounds were run on a Bruker AM-300L instrument operating at 300 MHz and 75.4 MHz, respectively, in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ solutions, unless otherwise stated.

3-Formylaminocoumarin (2) : A mixture of 3-hydroxycoumarin (1.00 g, 6.17 mmol) and distilled formamide (3 ml) was heated at 150–160° (bath temperature) for 2 h and cooled. The product solid mass was triturated with water (15 ml) and the brownish solid was filtered, washed with a little cold water and recrystallised from ethanol; white solid, m.p. 190°, yield 0.82 g (72%); ν_{max} 3340 (s, NH), 1670 and 1710 (both s, NCHO and C=O of coumarin), 1620, 1600, 1565, 1525 (s), 1450, 1400 (s), 1360, 1290, 1190, 1180, 1070, 910, 760 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 8.63 (1H, s, CH=O), 8.50 (1H, s, 4-H), 7.27 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, 5-H), 7.38–7.47 (2H, m, 6-H and 7-H), 7.21 (1H, d, J 8.6 Hz, 8-H), 8.21 (brs, NH); δ_{C} 159.48 (d, CH=O), 129.27 (d, C-4), 125.83 (d, C-5), 125.17 (d, C-7), 124.69 (d, C-6), 116.41 (d, C-8), 157.80 (s, C=O), 150.25 (s, C-8a), 123.21 (s, C-4a), 119.60 (s, C-3) (Found : C, 63.69; H, 3.88; N, 7.31. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires : C, 63.49; H, 3.70; N, 7.40%).

Hydrolysis of 3-formylaminocoumarin (2) to 3-aminocoumarin (3) : A mixture of 2 (2.25 g, 11.9 mmol) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid monohydrate (3.9 g, 20.5 mmol) was heated at 135–140° (internal temperature) with constant stirring in a oil-bath for 2 h, cooled and the post-reaction mixture was extracted with warm water (3 × 40 ml). The combined aqueous extract was made ammoniacal and cooled; the title compound was obtained as a pinkish white solid which recrystallised from ethanol as shining white flakes; yield 1.32 g (69%), m.p. 132° (lit.⁹ m.p. 130°); δ_{H} 6.66 (1H, s, H-8), 7.36 (1H, distorted d, 4-H), 7.13–7.24 (3H, m, H-5, H-6, H-7), 5.63 (2H, br s, -NH₂); δ_{C} 125.33 (d, C-5) 124.78 and 124.44 (both d, C-6, C-7), 115.39 (d, C-8), 107.78 (d, C-4), 158.61 (s, C-2), 147.92 (s, 8a), 133.25 (s, C-3), 121.39 (s, C-4a).

Benzo[1]pyran[4,3-d]oxazol-4-one (6) : A mixture of 4-hydroxycoumarin (2.00 g, 12.3 mmol) and freshly distilled formamide (5 ml) was taken in a 10 ml round-bottomed flask equipped with a reflux condenser and a NaOH filled guard-tube and heated with stirring in an oil-bath at 155–160° for 2 h. The post-reaction mixture was cooled and triturated with cold water (40 ml). The precipitated solid was filtered, washed well with cold water and recrystallised from ethanol; yield 1.92 g (84%), m.p. 222°; ν_{max} 3127, 1698 (s, C=O str.), 1625 (s, C=N) 1498,

1416, 1341, 1308, 1210, 1057 (s), 753 (s), 670, 449; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 381 (2.77), 310 (4.35), 268.5 (3.91), 260.5 (3.86), 254.5 (3.98), 246 (4.11), 231 (4.33) nm; λ_{min} (log ϵ) 379.5 (2.60), 271.5 (3.90), 262.5 (3.75), 258 (3.75), 252 (3.90), 244 (4.09) nm; δ_{H} 8.43 (1H, s, 2-H), 7.23 and 7.26 (both d, J 8.4 and 8.0 Hz respectively, 9-H and 6-H), 7.58 and 7.87 (both distorted t, 8-H and 7-H); δ_{C} 162.21 (d, C-2), 134.51 (d, C-9), 124.08 (d, C-8), 125.49 (d, C-7), 117.03 (d, C-6), 163.23 (s, C-4), 160.61 (s, C-9b), 154.44 (s, C-5a), 125.88 (s, C-3a), 120.58 (s, C-9a); m/z (GCMS, EtOH) 189 (100%), 174 (10%), 162 (11%), 133 (15%), 121 (38%), 92 (25%) (Found : C, 63.95; H, 2.87; N, 7.31. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_5\text{NO}_3$ requires : C, 64.17; H, 2.67; N, 7.49%).

Benzo[1]thiopyran[4,3-d]oxazol-4-one (8) : Similar procedure as above was followed on a mixture of 4-hydroxybenzo[*b*]thiopyran-2-one (7) (1.00 g, 5.6 mmol) and freshly distilled formamide (6 ml) to obtain a greenish white solid which was recrystallised from ethanol to a pinkish white solid 8, m.p. 232°; yield 1.00 g (88%); ν_{max} 3160, 1675 (s, C=O str.), 1630, 1570, 1550, 1440, 1390, 1350, 1255, 1220, 1125, 1110, 910, 750, 670, 625 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 381 (2.71), 335 (3.98), 301.5 (3.88), 267 (3.99), 258 (3.83), 252 (3.78), 246.5 (3.81), 231 (4.01), 208 (3.71); λ_{min} (log ϵ) 379.5 (2.63), 311.5 (3.77), 284 (3.79), 260 (3.69), 254.5 (3.71), 248.5 (3.70), 243 (3.71); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 9.43 (1H, s, H-2), 8.44 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, H-9), 7.94 (1H, d, J 7.9 Hz, H-6), 7.66 and 7.76 (each 1H, each t, J ~7.9 Hz, H-7 and H-8); δ_{C} (CDCl_3) 150.03 (d, $^2J_{\text{H}}$ 177.2 Hz, C-2), 132.74 (d, $^2J_{\text{H}}$ 165.2 Hz, C-9), 129.70 (d, $^2J_{\text{H}}$ 164.7 Hz, C-8), 128.79 (d, $^2J_{\text{H}}$ 165.5 Hz, C-7), 127.92 (d, $^2J_{\text{H}}$ 166.6 Hz, C-6), 178.87 (s, C-4), 163.77 (s, C-9b), 136.80 (s, C-9a), 132.37 (s, C-5a), 125.71 (s, C-3a); m/z (GCMS, EtOH) 205 (100%), 189 (31%), 162 (65%), 134 (20%), 104 (14%), 89 (24%) (Found : C, 59.03; H, 2.70; N, 6.63. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2\text{S}$ requires : C, 59.11; H, 2.46; N, 6.90%).

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Ray *et al.* : Studies on reaction of hydroxycoumarin compounds with formamide

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